

Enhance electrical impedance tomography with magnetic readings

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Abstract: Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) employs alternating current and voltage measurements to perform medical imaging of the patient's respiration. EIT is safe, non-invasive, and cost-effective but suffers from low spatial resolution and poor sensitivity away from the electrode locations. Here we compare the increase in sensitivity when magnetic readings are used instead of standard voltage readings in EIT. The simulated results show that the magnetic readings are up to a factor of one hundred more sensitive than standard EIT implementation.

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I. Introduction

Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is a medical imaging technique that uses electrical measurements to create images. Electrodes are used to inject small alternating currents and record the resulting voltages. Commonly applied at the bedside, EIT monitors patient ventilation by placing an electrode belt around the thorax. The recorded voltages are then processed to reconstruct the chest's conductivity distribution using a reconstruction algorithm. This reconstruction process involves solving an inverse problem through a forward model, which mathematically formulates the measurements. However, due to the intrinsic nonlinearity of the forward model and the reliance on peripheral measurements, the inverse problem is severely ill-posed. This makes achieving a stable solution difficult, resulting in low spatial resolution in EIT images.

However, some authors showed that enhancing the EIT with additional peripheral magnetic readings can improve the EIT inverse problem [1], [2].

In this contribution, we investigate through numerical simulations, the sensitivity of EIT toward a target placed in a homogeneous cylindrical tank compared with the same measurement where peripheral magnetic readings instead of voltage readings are taken.

II. Material and methods

Numerical simulations were performed using Finite Element Method (FEM) with Matlab package EIDORS version 3.11 [3]. The setup involved a cylindrical tank with a diameter and height of 0.2 meters. Inside the tank, a spherical object with a radius of 0.02 meters was placed. The tank had a conductivity of 0.503 S/m, while the object's

conductivity was 0.334 S/m. These represent the conductivity of muscle and deflated lung tissue, respectively at 1 MHz [4], [5]. The object was positioned along the central axis at four locations between -2 cm and 4 cm from the tank's center, which are areas where EIT has the least sensitivity. The current stimulation was set to 10 mA.

Sixteen electrodes were placed at the mid-height of the tank, and sixteen points for readings of the magnetic field were located between the electrodes. These readings were performed in cylindrical coordinates (θ , ρ and z). No noise was considered in the simulations. A reference measurement was taken without the object, and to quantify the sensitivity a normalized difference was calculated using the formula:

$$\Delta y_i = \frac{\|y_i^2 - y_{0,i}^2\|_2}{\|y_{0,i}^2\|_2}, \quad (1)$$

where y_i is the voltage of the EIT measurement or one of the three components of the magnetic field, $y_{0,i}$ is the same reading for the reference measurement, and $\|x\|_2$ is the Euclidian norm of the vector x .

III. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 a) shows the standard EIT measurements for the four object positions and part b) shows the normalized difference against the measurement without object. The EIT voltage measurements are not distinguishable from each other and the normalized difference is around 0.02.

Fig. 2 a-c) shows the three components of the magnetic field for the four object positions, while in parts d-f) there are the normalized differences. Apart from the z

Figure 1: a) EIT voltages for four different positions of the object. b) normalized difference (Eq. 1) against the reference measurement for the four different positions.

component, the magnetic readings have remarkably different trends. In particular, their normalized differences against the reference measurement are around two for the θ and ρ components and around 0.13 for the z component.

There is a notable difference between the measurements of the object made with standard EIT and with magnetic readings. For EIT the voltage trends were undistinguishable while there was a distinct difference in θ and ρ components of the magnetic field. On the other hand, the z component shows smaller deviations but still larger than for EIT.

This was highlighted by the normalized differences against the reference measurement which are almost a hundred times larger for the θ and ρ components of the magnetic field—but only six times for the z component—meaning that the magnetic readings are far more informative than the voltage readings for the same measurements.

However, only a simplified tank was taken into account in this investigation and the object was deliberately located in the position of minimal sensitivity for EIT.

Also, contrary to EIT measurements where the electrodes were properly simulated, the magnetic readings were ideal. In a real setup, however, the magnetic field needs to be integrated on non-infinitesimally small points which could reduce the sensitivity of the measurements.

Furthermore, noise was neglected and while its effect is well understood in an EIT setup this is not the case for magnetic readings. Also, the magnetic field values were in the order of 1 – 0.1 nT which are extremely challenging to recover in real life.

IV. Conclusions

EIT features low sensitivity toward objects located away from the electrodes. However, preliminary simulations showed that using magnetic readings instead of voltage readings could enhance the sensitivity toward these objects by a factor of up to one hundred.

Figure 2: a-c) the three components of the magnetic field for four different positions of the object. d-f) normalized difference (Eq. 1) against the reference measurement for the three components for the four different positions of the object.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

Research funding: Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) project TAP (project number 498224366) and H2020 MSCA Rise (#872488 DCPM), and ERA PerMED – FKZ (2522FSB903). Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest. Informed consent: the conducted research is not related to individuals. Ethical approval: the conducted research is not related to either human or animal use.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Gursoy, Y. Mamatjan, A. Adler, and H. Scharfetter, "Enhancing Impedance Imaging Through Multimodal Tomography," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 58, no. 11, pp. 3215–3224, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2011.2165714.
- [2] S. Levy, D. Adam, and Y. Bresler, "Electromagnetic impedance tomography (EMIT): a new method for impedance imaging," *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 676–687, Jun. 2002, doi: 10.1109/TMI.2002.800573.
- [3] A. Adler and W. R. B. Lionheart, "Uses and abuses of EIDORS: an extensible software base for EIT," *Physiol. Meas.*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. S25–S42, May 2006, doi: 10.1088/0967-3334/27/5/S03.
- [4] IT'IS Foundation, "Tissue Properties Database V4.0." 2018. doi: 10.13099/VIP21000-04-0.
- [5] C. Gabriel, "Compilation of the Dielectric Properties of Body Tissues at RF and Microwave Frequencies.," King's Coll London (United Kingdom) Dept of Physics, Jan. 1996. Accessed: Oct. 16, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://apps.dtic.mil/docs/citations/ADA303903>